

THE ACADEMIC MOBILITY OF THE TEACHERS AS A RAISING FACTOR OF THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8058324>

Abstract. *Issues of organization of academic mobility at the institute of higher education are considered. The notion of academic mobility at the institute of higher education, its goal, result, problems and ways of solving them are determined.*

Key words: *academic mobility, types, academic mobility programs, directions of development of international cooperation, internationalization, improving the quality of education.*

АКАДЕМИЧЕСКАЯ МОБИЛЬНОСТЬ ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЕЙ КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КАЧЕСТВА ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация. *Рассмотрены вопросы организации академической мобильности в вузе, а также определено понятие академической мобильности в вузе, ее цель, результат, проблемы и пути их решения.*

Ключевые слова: *академическая мобильность, виды, программы академической мобильности, направления развития международного сотрудничества, интернационализация, повышение качества образования.*

Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan in modern conditions is undergoing significant changes. The trend of higher education in Uzbekistan is aimed at the internationalization of the educational system. The internationalization process is focused on strengthening the intellectual potential of the country, borrowing the experience of international partner universities and integrating them into the domestic educational and research process, promoting Uzbek education, science and culture in the global educational market.

Prospects for the development of internationalization are supported by the interaction of partner universities, when each participant "shares" the strongest aspects of the educational process and research with partners, thereby improving the quality of education.

Developing the internationalization of education, the Republic of Uzbekistan provides an opportunity to increase the competitiveness of the Uzbekistan economy by adapting graduates to the global world in all areas of social development. The expediency of the process of internationalization in education is aimed at achieving the following goals: changing and increasing financial resources by attracting foreign students on a commercial basis, enlarging the regional interaction of the university with other organizations for the effective use of its resources, teaching its students in foreign partner universities, improving the quality of education and scientific research of students and teachers in the international educational space.

One of the tools in the training of teachers, which will improve the quality of education,

is academic mobility.

According to the definition of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe (2006), academic mobility means “the movement of someone associated with education for a specified (usually up to a year) period to another educational institution (in their own country or abroad) for training, teaching or research, after which the student, teacher or researcher returns to his primary school. This concept is not associated with emigration or a long period of study (work) abroad”¹.

In the Leuven Communiqué (2009) “The mobility of students, novice researchers and higher education staff improves the quality of programs and research. It enhances the academic and cultural internationalization of European higher education... Mobility is essential for personal development and employability; it builds respect for diversity and the ability to understand other cultures...”².

Academic mobility is aimed at the implementation of the following goals: improving the quality of education received by the student, introducing new methods and technologies in the learning process, participation of both students and teachers in the international education system, organizing conditions for employment of graduates, higher - increasing their competitiveness in the international labor market, as well as increasing the prestige of an educational organization in the world educational space.

Also, the problem of academic mobility was raised by Atamuratova Maftuna in her article. The author talks about academic mobility in terms of improving the quality of student education, and also as one of the main mechanisms of internationalization³.

The author talks about the need to support students of different genders through special programs in his article "Gender Equality in Education".⁴

Academic mobility of teaching staff in the field of educational and scientific activities can be carried out in the following forms:

- participation in advanced training programs, including internships;
- participation in conferences and seminars;
- participation in language and summer schools, in joint developments, etc.

The most successful academic mobility development programs include:

- The Erasmus program, which started in 1987 in the European Union. From 2014 to 2020, the Program was renamed Erasmus+. Its funding will amount to 14.7 million euros. According to the program, almost 270,000 students received EU grants to study abroad in

¹ Methodological recommendations for the development of the academic mobility of the students and university teachers in the higher educational institution. [electronic resource] http://www.bologna.ntf.ru/DswMedia/recom-mendations_mobility_vsues.pdf. [in Russian].

² Chistohvalov V.N. The condition, tendencies and problems of the academic mobility in the European higher education space. M.: RUDN, 2008. [in Russian].

³ Atamuratova M.M. Improving the pedagogical mechanisms of the process of internationalization of higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan.

⁴ Atamuratova M.M. Gender Equality in Education. Journal of Science and Innovation Volume 1 №13 Pages 65-67. [in Russian].

2012-2013.

- Scholarship programs of the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD). The service plays the role of an intermediary in the global educational space. The German Academic Exchange Service has fourteen foreign offices and about fifty information centers. When implementing academic exchanges, DAAD provides for about 60,000 scholarships per year.

- Fulbright program. In 2014, more than 1,500 Uzbek scientists, students, graduate students, and teachers received a Fulbright grant. Every year about 70 fellows come to the Republic of Uzbekistan for several programs.

The implementation of academic mobility of students "in its purest form" allows developing the following competencies: finding ways to interact with the world community, the ability to study the problem in a comparative aspect, the ability to cross-cultural communication, the ability to assess one's own level of knowledge, the ability to change self-perception, knowledge about other cultures. Academic mobility provides an impetus for the development of academic excellence through new contacts and perspectives, as well as the comparison of education systems. The absence of barriers in the field of education strengthens international cooperation and interconnection, and also improves the quality of higher education and research. To improve the quality of training of teaching staff, it is necessary to improve the model for organizing academic mobility of teaching staff of Uzbekistan universities. The development of academic mobility requires the solution of certain tasks: increasing the availability of choice and implementation of various educational trajectories for students within the framework of one or more basic educational programs; increasing the attractiveness of the proposed educational trajectories, as well as providing the opportunity for students to choose the most suitable trajectories for them, taking into account their personal characteristics, abilities, preferences, interests; creation of corporate information and educational, personnel and material and technical resources at the interuniversity level, as well as by organizing interaction with enterprises-strategic partners; formation of motivation for academic mobility for students.

As part of the project of the concept of modernization of teacher education, new approaches are being developed to the development and implementation of training programs for teachers. The changes affected the content and technologies of training teachers in accordance with professional standards, with the development of networking and academic mobility.

The implementation of the project "International Academic Mobility" is carried out in several directions: the formation of an international contractual framework for the recognition of documents on education and qualifications; formation of framework programs to support academic mobility, including the allocation of quotas by the Republic of Uzbekistan for the training of citizens of foreign states in educational institutions of higher education of the Uzbekistan; providing training for citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan in foreign educational organizations; attracting leading scientists to Uzbek educational organizations of higher professional education, scientific institutions of state academies of sciences and state research centers of the Republic of Uzbekistan; establishment of partnership relations between scientific and educational organizations.

1. Recognition of education and (or) qualifications obtained in a foreign state.

Information support for the recognition in the Republic of Uzbekistan of foreign education and (or) foreign qualifications is carried out by the national information center, the functions of which are performed by an organization authorized by the Republic of Uzbekistan. Such an organization is the state budgetary scientific institution “Main State Expert Center for Education Evaluation”.

Legal framework: about 70 bilateral and multilateral agreements on the recognition of education, about 20 draft agreements are under development.

2. Reception by foreign countries for training of Uzbek students, graduate students and scientific and pedagogical workers. Every year, foreign states, individual educational organizations, international organizations provide Uzbek citizens with the opportunity to study in various educational programs at the expense of the host country. A prerequisite for participation in such programs for obtaining scholarships is the training or work of the applicant for a foreign scholarship in a Uzbek educational organization. Information about proposals received by the Uzbekistan Ministry of Education and Science is sent to educational institutions subordinate to the Ministry.

3. International academic mobility of scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel.

The projects are implemented by the Department of Science and Technology of the Uzbekistan Ministry of Education and Science, the Department for Certification of Scientific and Scientific and Pedagogical Personnel of the Uzbekistan Ministry of Education and Science, as well as educational and scientific organizations. Educational and scientific organizations ensure the direction of pedagogical and scientific workers of Uzbek organizations engaged in educational activities to foreign educational organizations, which includes the admission of foreign pedagogical and scientific workers to Uzbek educational organizations engaged in educational activities, for the purpose of training, advanced training and improvement of scientific and educational activities.

4. International academic mobility of students.

Network interaction of educational organizations in the implementation of educational programs, including the mechanism for offsetting the results of mastering certain parts of the educational program in third-party organizations. Transfer from one organization to another for a certain period of time, in relation to students in basic professional educational programs.

The project is implemented by the Department of State Policy in the Sphere of Higher Education, the Department of State Policy in the Sphere of General Education, the Department of State Policy in the Sphere of Training of Workers and AVE, and educational organizations.

5. Confirmation of documents on education and (or) qualifications issued by Russian organizations engaged in educational activities.

Confirmation of documents on education and (or) qualifications by affixing an apostille on them is carried out by the executive authorities of the subjects of the Republic of Uzbekistan exercising the powers transferred to them by the Republic of Uzbekistan to confirm documents on education and (or) qualifications, upon applications citizens submitted in writing or in the form of electronic documents using public information and telecommunication networks, including the Internet, including a single portal of state and municipal services.

In the education system, the quality of educational processes, training and retraining of personnel, advanced training of teachers, certification and state accreditation of all types of state and non-state educational organizations, non-state education. Licensing of educational institutions, organization of recognition of educational documents issued in foreign countries, apostille of official documents issued by educational and scientific organizations, compilation of a rating of educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. One of the main tasks of the State Inspectorate is to make announcements.

The State Inspectorate also provides training in the education system for heads of educational and scientific organizations on issues of quality control of the educational process, teaching staff, training and retraining of personnel. Has the right to suspend the execution of orders, resolutions and decisions taken in violation. relevant legislation.

The State Inspectorate carries out its activities in the following areas:

1. Certification and state accreditation of educational institutions
2. Quality control of teaching staff, legalization, recognition and nostrification of education documents
3. Monitoring and quality control of education in the system of continuous education
4. Deadlines for filing and consideration of applications.

The implementation of the direction in the state educational policy "International academic mobility", the improvement of existing tools and mechanisms to support the mobility of teaching staff, the creation of new mechanisms for the development and quality of mobility, the formation of favorable legal, infrastructural, socio-economic conditions will contribute to the achievement targets set in national strategic documents and international agreements.

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